

DEMOGRAPHIC CHANGES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY OF CHINA AND UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the demographic indicators of China. In addition, the demographic policies of some countries are shown, the nationalities living in China and the analysis of gender indicators are described socio-economic growth in Uzbekistan and the concept of demography, social protection, market economy, demographic processes and their factors, sources of studying demographic processes, activism in democratic change.*

Keywords: *demographic change, population policy, economic growth, growth dynamics, age structure, gender breakdown, country, socio-economic, demographic, valuation, dividend, development, innovation*

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence, taking into account the current real economic and demographic situation, a mechanism of social protection has been created during the gradual transition to a market economy. Population policy is the purposeful activity of state institutions and other social institutions in regulating the process of population reproduction. Population policy is an integral part of general socio-economic policy as well as an integral part of population policy. The need for population policy - the influence of the state on the birth process - regardless of population status and population growth rates as recognized by almost all countries in the world.¹

Depending on demographics, there are two main types of policies: those aimed at increasing birth rates (typical of economically developed countries) and lowering birth rates (necessary in developing countries). Often, the actual implementation of population policy is fraught with moral and ethical difficulties and a lack of financial resources. The term "birth control" is used to describe a country's influence on the fertility process, primarily to reduce its levels and maintain the country's population growth rate.²

The goals and objectives of population policy are usually reflected in political programs and declarations. In general, the goal of population policy is usually to develop an ideal population growth pattern that maintains or alters the dynamics of population size and structure, rates of change, birth dynamics, mortality rates, family structure, migration, internal and external migration, population quality feature.

Demographic objects.³ Politicians can be the population, socio-demographics of an entire country or individual regions. Groups, groups of people, specific types of households, or life cycle stages. The main feature of population policy is that it affects the dynamics of the population

¹ Q.X.Abdurahmonov, Demografiya. O'quv qo'llanma 5A340114-“Mehnat iqtisodiyoti” magistratura mutaxassisligi talablariga mo'ljallangan .—T.:Noshir,2011.-296 b.

² Медков В.М. Основы демографии: серия «учебники и учебные пособия».- Ростов-на-Дону : «Феникс», 2003 г.- 448с.

³ Демография: Учебник для вузов. – М.: Логос, 2005. – 280 с. Под редакцией Н.А. Волгина и Л.Л. Рыбаковского.

process not directly, but indirectly through population behavior, through decisions in areas such as marriage, family, fertility, career choice, work, place of residence, etc.

The main directions of population policy include: State support for families with children, creating conditions to combine parents with active occupational activities, reducing morbidity and mortality, increasing average life expectancy, and improving the quality of life of the population. Improve property, oversee the relocation process, urbanization and resettlement, etc. Population policies are usually implemented through a range of different measures:

- Economic (leaves and various allowances paid for the birth of a child; child allowances according to the number of children, age, type of family; loans, loans, tax and housing benefits, etc.);

- Administrative and legal (laws on marriage, divorce, the status of children in the family, alimony obligations, maternal and child protection, abortion and the use of contraceptives; social security for persons with disabilities, working conditions and working conditions for working women) mothers, internal and external migration, etc.);

- Educational and advocacy measures aimed at shaping public opinion, population norms and standards of conduct, and the specific demographic climate of society.

Types of Population Policy

1. Policies to increase the local population (implemented in economically developed countries in North America and Western Europe).

2. Policies to reduce population growth rates, reducing the absolute size of their populations in some countries.

3. Stimulus (birth) policies (implemented in countries with low population density and high birth rates per unit of territory).

4. The policy of stabilizing the population is called the optimal fixed population policy.

According to world experience, then economically developed countries, those seeking to increase the population, eliminate the population crisis or at least maintain the quality and quantity of the population with systematic measures to protect children, care for mothers with children - measures taken, allocation of loans to newlyweds, introduction of family allowances ; Special measures are being developed and tax, immigration and housing policies are being implemented. In countries with high population density and high birth rates (over 2.3% per year), policies to limit population growth are often implemented. In this context, family planning becomes the basic foundation of public policy in the field of family and population. Birth rates are constantly controlled and regulated by law. The best family type is two children or even one child.

To this end, early marriage is prohibited, abortion is permitted, family planning is promoted, and necessary medicines and medical assistance are provided. In most cases, immigration policy measures and employment policies are used. In many Asian and African countries, the achievement of these goals is hindered by the low literacy and education levels of the majority of the population,

limited access to information, lack of necessary funding and relevant experts, and often resistance to national cultural traditions.

The experience of Asian powers such as China and India shows that birth control policies are ineffective and are often actively rejected. As a result, governments in these countries have had to mitigate the impact of economic, political and immigration on fertility dynamics, not only in rural areas but also in urban areas.

Special positions on population issues are characteristic of most Latin American countries. They believe their territories are underpopulated and any outside effort to lower the birth rate would be considered foreign interference. Internal policies of the people that are incompatible with moral, ethical and national traditions and economic interests. Population and Economic Growth In the author's economic article, social labor productivity in different countries is not only a demographic factor that has been demonstrated many times, but is often a complex and contradictory process involving conflicting factors and trends.

A diagram consisting of four blue-bordered boxes arranged in a descending staircase pattern from top-left to bottom-right. Each box contains a numbered point. The boxes are connected by a blue triangular shape pointing downwards.

1. Under the conditions of the expansion of population reproduction, the growth of social labor productivity is possible due to the structural changes of various economic sectors and the employment of laborers.

2. With the expansion of the domestic market and the improvement of the profitability of large enterprises, the improvement of social productivity is entirely possible.

3. As a result of globalization, technological progress has also covered those countries that have surpassed modernization, which has led to an increase in the amount of knowledge that has brought back the living workforce of these countries.

4. The population concentration that occurs in the context of its growth also contributes to increasing the country's labor productivity.

Population policy is a system of national measures aimed at creating the most favorable patterns of population growth and settlement for social development. It may include measures to reduce mortality by standardizing external and internal processes, streamlining them, and improving medical services, but one of its main tasks is a variety of economic, social, administrative, legal and advocacy tools. Economic measures: Paid maternity leave and various benefits, child benefits depending on their number, age, family type, loans, taxes and housing benefits, etc. Administrative legal instruments include laws regulating marriage, divorce, family status of children, alimony obligations, maternal and child protection, abortion, use of contraceptives, social support for persons with disabilities, working conditions and labor systems. Female mothers, internal and external migration. Publicity and educational activities aimed at forming public opinion, norms and standards of population behavior that determine socio-demographic conditions play an important role in reproduction. In reality, the choice of means to influence birth rates varies widely, depending on the task and its level of scientific validity, social conditions, and the actual capabilities of the country.

The greatest development and dissemination of population policies occurred in the second half of the 20th century, which is associated with significant regional differences in the world's natural growth. On the one hand, population explosions have occurred in many regions, resulting in a complex socio-economic situation; on the other hand, population decline and aging in developed countries are rapidly approaching a crisis of democracy.

In Western European countries, the system of population policy measures is broadly similar, although, of course, there are differences in various payment amounts and other benefits. According to demographers, the most aggressive policies to stimulate birth rates and natural growth were implemented in Sweden.

In Russia, when it was part of the Soviet Union, population policy was largely reduced to implementing comprehensive measures to encourage and provide material and spiritual stimulation for extended families. In the late 1980s, when births and natural growth began to decline, these measures were reinforced by difficult market transitions and were complemented by several new measures to protect families with children. One of the causes of this crisis, and one of its consequences, is the increase in the number of abortions, which is now the uncompetitive number one in the world in terms of its total number. In the late 1990s. An action plan was drawn up for the withdrawal of the Russian Federation from the population crisis.⁴

Analysis and result

A glance at the diagram provided reveals data on the proportion of distribution by age over fifth year between 2018 and 2022, a particular intriguing highlighted fact by chart was covered 0-4 child's age about less than 4 billion. During the period age of able to work year by year increased after introducing developing strategy, after the pandemic each age coped with this difficult situation in own way.

⁴ Щербаков А.И., М.Г. Мдинарадзе, А.Д. Назаров, Е.А. Назарова ; Демография : учеб. пособие / под общ. ред. д-ра экон. наук, проф. А.И. Щербакова. — М. : ИНФРА-М, 2017. — 216 с.

The pie chart illustrates the percentage of middle age people by ageing over this period that showed last one. However humanity who live in Uzbekistan almost young people it seem in this circular the highest percentage introducing of teenagers about lees than ten.

Ancient Chinese nation. av. It was created on the basis of Sino-Tibetan, Altai, Austro-Asian and Austrian languages due to its merger with many countries in the sixth and seventh centuries. Therefore, in the later history and the development of modern China, ethnic minorities constituted the majority. China's population includes about 50 ethnic groups, divided into different language groups: 93.3% are Chinese, and ethnic minorities include Huiyi, Uyghur, Manchu, Yidu, Tibetan, Bu, and Miao.⁵

With the founding of the People's Republic of China, the first census was conducted in 1953, when the population was estimated at 582.6 million people (excluding Taiwan). The second registration in 1964 made 698.6 million people. In the summer of 1982, the third registration, 1.0082 billion people, saw the indicator of one billion people for the first time. In 1990, the population of China's 29 provinces and autonomous regions was 1.16 billion. As a result, the population of the People's Republic of China increased from 542 to 1.16 trillion in 1949-1990 to 618 million, an average absolute increase of 15 million. By the middle of the 20th century, the population had increased by 50-60 million people, with an annual growth rate of 0.3%.

Table 1. PRC population growth dynamics.

Year	Population	Population growth %
2011	1 372 685 709	0.56 %

⁵ Sadibekva B.Dj. Xitoy iqtisodiyoti III qism –Toshkent 2011. – 131 b.

2012	1 380 373 083	0.56 %
2013	1 388 076 421	0.56 %
2014	1 395 699 763	0.55 %
2015	1 403 181 303	0.54 %
2016	1 410 468 287	0.52 %
2017	1 417 564 227	0.50 %
2018	1 424 362 022	0.48 %
2019	1 430 740 957	0.45 %
2020	1 436 568 870	0.41 %
2021	1 443 981 565	0.52 %
2022	1 451 432 510	0.52 %

The table was prepared by the author based on <http://countrymeters.info/ru/China>

The table shows that the population growth has a different trend every year, but has the characteristics of growth. That is, an increase of 1% or 3% per year is visible. In fact, it grew at a maximum rate of 0.53%, not as high as it was in the 90s. Also, despite the new laws, the rate of growth has not changed. There are forecasts that this trend will increase in the coming years.

The distribution of the population into groups by age was divided according to the following trend:

The diagram was prepared by the author based on <http://countrymeters.info/ru/China>

As you can see from this graph, the largest segment of the population is middle-aged, which means the population is aging. The working-age population is decreasing year by year. In addition, the increase in the elderly raises various social problems (affecting insurance, pensions, living standards). The main thing is that the next generation may need extra effort to keep the economy running smoothly.

The diagram table was prepared by the author based on <http://countrymeters.info/ru/China>

As we all know, the reason for China's disproportionate population started many years ago, that is, it has become a problem for people of married age. ⁶There is a large number of women in the under 64 age group, but there is an increase in the number of women in terms of the composition of the elderly.

The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, currently approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017. The development of economic activity through the development of its activities serves as a basis for social protection.

Another achievement of the country's social policy is the emergence of a system of social services, the widespread use of modern methods and technologies that allow to provide effective social assistance to citizens in working with the population. Along with the establishment and development of local self-government bodies - the provision of regional social services in the authorities, the training of specialists in the field of social work, social pedagogy and applied psychology, the possibility of providing social services to the population has increased.

⁶ Gu Baochang The China Population and Labor Yearbook, Volume 1, pp 1-32, 2009

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In this table main health indicators how role of ambulatory polyclinics very important. Population Uzbekistan is year by year growth that’s way we improve our medicine. We need more specialist doctor and medical workers, in ambulatory polyclinics in case people apply more than other medical clinics.

Changes in a person's life lead to changes in the population in this way. The movement of people from one place to another has an impact on the population and makeup of those places.

⁷ www.stat.uz

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As we can see in Uzbekistan migration situation is processing in this diagram show Uzbek people more departures than arrive. Even those Covid-19 time majorities left their home. Humans who arrive their home also not the same over 10 years ago probably their percentage increase specially all of them arrive to Uzbekistan from Asia and Russia .

Conclusion

In the era of globalization, the digital economy provides many advantages for government agencies; other industries also have their pros and cons. Electronic reports, invoices, electronic portal there are more than 20 directions and in all districts and cities there are branches of a single window and a center of public services in Uzbekistan.

Differences between the Western model and the Chinese UX design model

The typical Western consumer journey is a circular journey with four or five phases:

⁸ www.stat.uz

It turns out that such a model isn't relevant for the Chinese Market:

For the first phase of the conversion tunnel, the Chinese consumer compares in a different way than his counterparts. Chinese customers rely mainly on user-generated content that can be considered as more authentic and trustworthy. They are skeptical when it comes to business-generated content, such as websites or traditional advertising. They have a very strong trust in their family, friends and other Key Opinion Leaders (KOL). This is one of the reasons for their strong activity on social networks.

Because the first phase is much more developed on the Chinese model, the choice is often already made before the prospect arrives in store or on the e-shop. Online platforms are designed to provide, at the same time, convenient content and services for consumers to choose products, place orders and finish payments.

This is a direct consequence of the interconnection of platforms. The Chinese customer requires a consistent service among all channels, such as when he wants to return an online purchased product to an offline store. Flexibility is therefore eagerly awaited on this point. It's necessary to be particularly vigilant because the touch points are once again diverse and interconnected. For example, offline experience centers only serve as a complimentary channel that provides high-quality consumer and membership services.

Chinese customers like to share their opinions after the purchase of a product as they also rely on the opinions of others before buying. Thus, the way a company is able to shape a positive customer experience before, during and after the conversion, influences the customer's decision to become loyal or even to become a prescriber.

So a big difference is that the Chinese consumer enters the loyalty loop more quickly and the challenge is then to make your consumer stick in this loyalty loop.

However, although there is theoretical understandings of the Chinese customer journey, experts in Consumer Experience Management in China at Daxue Consulting truly believe that a customer journey map is unique and has to be designed ex nihilo for each brand.

REFERENCES

1. Blomm D., D. Canning and P. Malaney.2000. “Demographic Change and Economic Growth in Asia.” Population and Development Review 26 (suppl.) 257-290

2. Sang-Hyop Lee, Andrew Mason. Who gains from the demographic dividend? Forecasting income by age. *International journal of Forecasting* 23 (2007) 603-619.
3. DEMOGRAPHIC DIVIDEND, DIGITAL INNOVATION, AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: BANGLADESH EXPERIENCE Kazi Arif Uz Zaman and Tapan Sarker No. 1237 March 2021
4. Mason, A., *Demographic Transition and Demographic Dividends in Developed and Developing Countries*, Presented at United Nations Expert Group Meeting on Social and Economic Implications of Changing Population Age Structures, 31 August – 2.
5. McCarthy, K.F., (2001), *World population shifts: boom or doom?*, RAND; Population Matters.
6. Демография: Учебник для вузов. – М.: Логос, 2005. – 280 с. Под редакцией Н.А. Волгина и Л.Л. Рыбаковского.
7. Медков В.М. Основы демографии: серия «учебники и учебные пособия».- Ростов-на-Дону : «Феникс», 2003 г.- 448с.
8. Борисов В.А. Демография: учебник для ВУЗов.- М.: «Нота Бене» медиа трейд компания, 2003 г. – 344 с.
9. Зверев Н.В. Основы демографии: учебное пособие.- М.: «Высшая школа», 2004 г. – 374 с.
10. Бутов В.И. Демография: учебное пособие/под ред. Игнатова В.Г.- М.: «МарТ», Ростов-на-Дону: издательский центр «МарТ», 2003 г. – 592 с.
11. Q.X.Abdurahmonov, Demografiya. O’quv qo’llanma 5A340114–“Mehnat iqtisodiyoti” magistratura mutaxassisligi talablariga mo’ljallangan .–T.:Noshir,2011.-296 b.
12. Sadibekva B.Dj. Xitoy iqtisodiyoti III qism –Toshkent 2011. – 131 b.
13. Щербakov А.И., М.Г. Мдинарадзе, А.Д. Назаров, Е.А. Назарова ; Демография : учеб. пособие / под общ. ред. д-ра экон. наук, проф. А.И. Щербакoвa. — М. : ИНФРА-М, 2017. — 216 с.
14. Gu Baochang The China Population and Labor Yearbook, Volume 1,pp 1-32, 2009
15. http://www.policyproject.com/pubs/generalreport/Demo_Div.pdf
16. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350055033 LESSON 1 DEMOGRAPHIC DIVIDEND](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350055033_LESSON_1_DEMOGRAPHIC_DIVIDEND)
17. <https://populationeducation.org/what-demographic-dividend/>
18. www.Stat.uz
19. <https://strategy.uz>
20. <https://Populationeducation.org>
21. <https://daxueconsulting.com/work-kols-china/>